

LOCALIZING THE AREAS OF VECTOR-BORNE DISEASE RISK FROM THE ABUNDANCE OF CULEX PIPIENS SL.

M. C. Proença

University of Lisbon, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Physics, Lisbon, Portugal

M. T. Rebelo

University of Lisbon, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Animal Biology, Lisbon, Portugal

M. J. Alves

University of Lisbon, Faculty of Sciences, Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies (CESAM), Lisbon, Portugal

REVIVE Team

National Health Institute Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), Águas de Moura, Portugal

Abstract

This work characterizes the environment of *Culex pipiens* sl. in Portugal, using a 7-year data set collected all over the territory from May to October each year. *Culex pipiens* sl. are the most abundant mosquito complex in Portugal mainland and of medical importance, as they act as vectors for more than 20 species of virus.

The abundance data of mosquitoes' females is used with environmental factors in a geographic information system (GIS) to characterize its habitat, using land use/land cover data, distance to cartographed water bodies, altitude, and latitude. The distribution of mosquitoes by each factor shows mosquito preferences and identifies thresholds between areas of higher/lower abundance for i) altitude in intervals of 100 m, ii) degree of latitude and iii) distance to water in intervals of 1000 m; in the case of land use/land cover, the subset of the most populated classes is identified and aggregated. These thresholds allow the segmentation of the corresponding maps, and the area in common for all the environmental factors considered identifies the area where the risk of disease transmission is significant.

To categorize the risk in this broad area and focus mitigation countermeasures, we use the quantity of captures above average from all the data set to identify three categories of increased risk, which allow for a more targeted use of countermeasures and a detailed mitigation planning. This methodology can be used for any other vectors of medical importance, whenever abundance data is available, contributing to reduce costs and human labor and saving the environment from extensive application of toxic products.

Keywords: *Culex pipiens* sl., transmission risk, GIS, vector-borne diseases

INTRODUCTION

This case study characterizes the environment of *Culex pipiens* sl. in Portugal mainland based in its abundance, using a data set collected during seven years (2006-2012) from May to October all over the territory. The data set consists of 2,181 bulletins, containing records of 37,094 female mosquitoes and it's linked to environmental factors in a geographic information system (GIS). Several works in this line can be found (Kalluri, 2007), (Beck, 2000) and the basics of the methodologies, although rather diverse, were also inventoried (Dale, 1998).

The environmental factors used here to characterize the vector habitat are land use/land cover,

distance to cartographed water bodies, altitude, and latitude. Focus is on mosquito females, which gonotrophic cycle mate-bloodmeal-oviposition is responsible for the virus transmission; its abundance is the key for the planning of prophylactic countermeasures in delimited areas of disease transmission risk and to focus mitigation measures to avoid outbreaks of vector-borne diseases. Both total and females' mosquito figures were detailed in the data set. The same methodology can be applied to other vectors, whenever national surveillance abundance data is available; the cartography is worldwide available (Hay, 2006) and the computational requirements are the usual find in a current laptop.

MATERIAL

The data set is issued from a long-term vector surveillance program – REVIVE – a net of vector surveillance implemented by the Health Ministry, with the local labor of each of the five regional administrations of health (ARS). No sampling plan has been previously elaborated, so time and location of the captures was scheduled by the local agents doing the field work; trapping was carried out from May through October, with traps staying on site for one night.

The data base includes many other vectors, but the focus of interest in the *Culex pipiens* complex is justified by its medical importance: the females bite all warm-blooded vertebrates and are involved in the circulation of several arbovirus of concern to human health, like West Nile virus (Hamer, 2008) iridoviruses, rheoviruses and parvoviruses (Vinogradova, 2000).

The average capture is defined as the number of females caught divided by the number of traps used in one night, at each place. The average capture for each ARS, from North to South, is shown in Figure 1. Only at Alentejo and Algarve the figures are larger than the overall average value of the data set, 17.0.

Figure 5. Portugal mainland, with capture areas in the five ARSs and their average in each region.

The land use/land cover information used is part of the data base issued from the CORINE Programme (Co-ordination of Information on the Environment). Basically, it's an inventory of land cover with a hierarchical nomenclature of 44 classes: a program of the European Union aiming to build a uniform data base at a scale 1:100 000, with a minimum unity cartographed of 25 ha.

From 1985 to 1990, the European Commission implemented the CORINE Programme, and now it's a responsibility of the European Environment Agency (EEA).

6th ASIA PACIFIC International Modern Sciences Congress

We use the data base from 2006. Two kinds of satellites provided imagery for CLC2006 project (Butner, 2012),

- French SPOT-4/5 (60 km swath width, 20 m pixels; VIS, NIR and SWIR bands)
- Indian IRS P6 LISS III (141 km swath width, 23 m pixels; VIS, NIR and SWIR bands).

The altimetry came from the digital elevation data (DEM) obtained by the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM), an international project spearheaded by the U.S. National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA) and the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) that has covered more than 80% of the Earth's solid surface during a 11-day mission of the Space Shuttle Endeavour in February 2000. The SRTM data is available as 3 arc second (approx. 90m ground resolution) and has a vertical error reported to be less than 16 m (<https://www.usgs.gov>).

We had access to a version made available by University of Porto, which has been projected to ETRS89 PT-TM06 and resampled to a ground resolution of 80 m (<https://www.fc.up.pt>).

The information concerning cartographed water was available online from Serviço Nacional de Informação de Recursos Hídricos (<https://snirh.apambiente.pt>). Different layers contain rivers, reservoirs, lagoons, etc. The focus on stagnant water led to the selection of the layers containing lagoons, marshes, and reservoirs; after some discussion, the rivers were included, for favoring the creation of large pools of stagnant water along the banks and in the estuary. These digital layers have elements of three different types: polygonal (reservoirs of dams, lagoons, and estuaries), linear (rivers) and punctual (marshes).

METHODOLOGY

Two criteria were used to compare the environmental parameters associated with the captures (altitude, land use/land cover, distance to water, latitude), to establish a suitability discrimination: the distribution of the average captures for the interval considered, and the percentage of above average captures in each class/interval to be compared. The average of the overall data set is 17.0 *Culex pipiens* females per trap and night.

To be sure that our choice of a threshold or the selection of a group of classes was the best, we compare the two large groups resulting from the splitting using statistical Levene's test for variances and the appropriate test for means at a 95% confidence level.

The original 44 classes of land use/land cover data were aggregate to the appropriate classes to establish the report with mosquito activity and habitat preferences. This aggregation was achieved merging several of the Corine Land Cover (CLC) classes in 11 classes that synthetize the common interest of each subset, and they are Forest, Heterogeneous cultures, Permanent cultures, Small vegetation, Human presence, Human uninhabited, Temporary, Coastal and Natural wetlands, Bare soil and Water bodies.

This spatial aggregation was achieved in a Geographic Information System (GIS) (ArcMap from ESRI). The resulting layer is a simplified thematic map, especially in detailed areas, as it can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 6. Illustration of the difference corresponding to the original CLC with 44 possible classes (left) versus the same area with the aggregation to 11 classes (right).

One of the classes (Bare soil) has no records associate with it, so only 10 aggregate classes were used. The score of these 10 classes shows (Figure 3) an average capture higher than the overall average in Heterogeneous cultures, Forest and Small vegetation, although three more classes have meaningful scores compared to the four less representative ones, which are Permanent cultures, Coastal and Natural wetlands and Urban uninhabited, all with an average capture below 2.5 individuals.

Figure 7. Average capture in each class.

For the altitude data, the orthometric altitude for each record was extracted and interpolated at each capture point. In the range found in the data [-15 m, 941 m] we consider intervals of 100 m between 100 and 900 m and averaged the captures for each interval (Figure 4).

Figure 8. Average capture size by interval of altitude.

The *Culex pipiens* depend on the presence of water to complete their life cycle, and disease transmission requires the completion of at least one gonotrophic cycle before pathogen transfer occurs (Bentley, 1989) as the transmission is a collateral effect of the blood meal needed for the oviposition. Their preference seems to go for standing water with large amounts of organic content, which turns out to be the case for most spots of standing water.

The water bodies' cartographed are indicative of the presence of the standing water needed, but there are many small water containers, natural and man-made, that it's not possible to referencing. So, we worked with the set of layers previously mentioned (reservoirs, lagoons, estuaries, marshes, and rivers) establishing the minimum Euclidean distance to the nearest water body, and its type.

The global trends with intervals of 1000 m (Figure 5) shows the average capture have a clear decrease at distances greater than 3 km.

Figure 9. Average capture and distance to a cartographed water body.

The set of observations allowed also to analyze the latitudes where the *Culex pipiens* spp. abundance is more significant. The places of capture range from 37.021600 to 42.044911 decimal degrees latitude; although the Est-West coverage is not perfect along this range, with a large area (8.5W to 6.8W degrees) lacking information between 40 and 41 degrees, the North-South sampling is more regular.

Figure 10. Places of capture – the sampling ensures a reasonable North-South coverage.

The percentages of all captures that took place below 39 degrees of latitude is 86.7% (Table 1), even if the number of traps placed above 41° is the largest (686), which drive us to evaluate the average capture by degree of latitude.

Table 1. Distribution of the captures by interval of latitude

Latitude interval	Number of traps	Sum of captures	Percentage
Lat <38.0	511	17.988	48.5%
38.0 ≤ Lat <39.0	472	14.157	38.2%
39.0 ≤ Lat <40.0	120	1.103	3.0%
40.0 ≤ Lat <41.0	392	2.065	5.6%
Lat ≥ 41.0	686	1.781	4.8%

The average catch below 39° of latitude is higher than 30 individuals (**Error! Reference source not found.**), which overcomes largely the overall average of 17.0. Southern latitudes has the largest figures.

Figure 11. Average catch of *Culex pipiens* females by interval of latitude.

The supremacy of the southern latitudes is enhanced when the average captures are detailed by month (Figure 8), which shows that only in July the size of the catches in latitudes above 39° attains the global average size; latitude 39° is a clear threshold in *Culex pipiens* abundance.

Figure 12. Average capture of *Culex pipiens* females per month at each interval of latitude

GIS IMPLEMENTATION

The environmental conditioning founded through the analysis of mosquito's abundance previously described was applied to delimitation of areas with those characteristics in a geographic information system (ArcMap from ESRI), creating tree masks:

- the distance of 3000 m from the water is represented by a buffer contouring all the cartographed water bodies. The water distance was processed separately for rivers and the set of lagoons, reservoir dams, marshes, and estuaries because of its nature in a GIS: rivers are the only linear feature among the water layers.
- for the altitude, the 400 m threshold was applied to the raster DEM, cutting off the higher altitudes, that in the case of Portugal are mainly at north.
- the 6 land use/land cover classes with major abundance were separated.

The crossing of these 3 spatial conditions gives the area where the abundance of the vector is most

noticeable (Figure 9).

Figure 13. Area of higher probability of *Culex pipiens* sl. presence.

CATEGORIZATION OF RISK

Among the area identified by the abundance of *Culex pipiens* (Figure 9) as having high probability of presence and therefore, an increase transmission risk for humans, it was possible to discriminate 3 sets of conditions expressing categories of risk, using the same methodology previously described and the distribution of the 342 captures above average, that shows features that can be used to target only those areas where the mosquito population becomes critical. We present as example the distance of the captures above average to a water body.

Figure 14. Distribution of above average captures to water body distance.

Figure 10 shows that 81% of all the captures above average were made in a distance of less than 1 km from a water body, and 16.7 % in the next interval, but still at less than 2 km from the water. A minority of these captures (2.3%) took place far than 2 km and none was registered after the 3 km mark.

The same reasoning is made for the other two factors, Altitude and Land use/Land cover. Assuming

that the abundance of *Culex pipiens* females represents a health risk, the criteria issued from this analysis can define three areas of increasing risk:

1 – Minimum risk

Distance to water bodies < 3000 m

Altitude < 300 m

LU/LC classes included: Heterogeneous cultures, Small vegetation, Forest, Temporary wetlands, Human presence and Water bodies.

2 – Medium risk

Distance to water bodies < 2000 m

Altitude < 200 m

LU/LC classes included: Heterogeneous cultures, Small vegetation, Forest and Temporary wetlands

3 – High risk

Distance to water bodies < 1000 m

Altitude < 100 m

LU/LC classes included: Heterogeneous cultures, Small vegetation

The advantage of a GIS is that these results can be translated to maps and released to the stakeholders to target the counter measure level needed at each location. The three areas are superposed in Figure 11.

Figure 15. The three area of increased risk using female abundance as a proxy.

The highest risk area is small and can be perfectly localized, as well as the other two areas, superposing the areas of interest defined in the GIS as masks in the conventional cartography (Figure 12).

Figure 16. Separation of the areas of increased risk: a) minimum risk, b) medium risk and c) maximum risk.

This categorization of the risk can help stakeholders to target the harsher countermeasures, including products that are toxic to other animal species, and to save human labor and costs, because the high-risk areas are reduced and well localized, and more efficient use of mitigation measures can be targeted.

CONCLUSIONS

The case study presented shows the methodology to apply at an abundance data set of any vector in order to evaluate its ecological niche and establish the limits for areas of increased risk of transmission for vector-borne diseases. In this implementation we use environmental factors, but many others can also be used, according to our knowledge of the habits and characteristics of vector species, or the conditions for survival and replication of pathogens whenever they are known. The application of this methodology for a large area allows to plan and detail different countermeasures levels according to the local scale of the problem. The resources used in this implementation (all the exogenous data) were available online.

REFERENCES

- Kalluri S., Gilruth P., Rogers D., Szczur M. 2007. Surveillance of arthropod vector-borne infectious diseases using remote sensing techniques: a review. *PLoS Pathog.* 3(10)
- Beck, L.R., Lobitz, B.M., Wood, B.L. 2000. Remote sensing and human health: new sensors and new opportunities. *Emerg Infect Dis.* 6(3), pp. 217-227. doi:10.3201/eid0603.000301
- Dale, P.E.R., Ritchie, S.A., Territo, B.M., Morris, C.D., Muhar, A., Kay, B.H. 1998. An Overview of Remote Sensing and GIS for Surveillance of Mosquito Vector Habitats and Risk Assessment, *Journal of Vector Ecology*, 23(1), pp. 54-61
- Hay S., Tatem A., Graham A., Goetz S., Rogers D. 2006. Global environmental data for mapping infectious disease distribution. *Adv. Parasitol.* 62, pp. 37–77.
- Hamer, G. L., Kitron, U. D., Brawn, J. D., Loss, S. R., Ruiz, M. O., Goldberg, T. L. and Walker, E. D. 2008. *Culex pipiens pipiens* (Diptera: Culicidae): A Bridge Vector of West Nile Virus to Humans, *J. Med. Entomol.* 45(1): pp. 125-128
- Vinogradova, E. B. 2000. *Culex pipiens pipiens* mosquitoes: taxonomy, distribution, ecology, physiology, genetics, applied importance and control, Pensoft Series Parasitologica N. 2, ISBN 954-642-103-0
- Bütner, G., Kosztra, B., Maucha, G. and Pataki, R. 2012. Implementation and achievements of CLC2006, Institute of Geodesy, Cartography and Remote Sensing (FÖMI)
<https://sniamb.apambiente.pt>
<https://www.dgterritorio.pt>
<https://www.usgs.gov>
<https://www.fc.up.pt/pessoas/jagoncal/srtm>
<https://snirh.apambiente.pt>